

Urinary Mucosal Cryoglobulin: A Review

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Abstract : The procedure for the assessment of the urinary mucosal cryoglobulin (UMCG) is being reviewed, testified and evaluated. The major features of UMCG are rather similar to that of serum cryoglobulin. Such evident similarities are forming the reality for the existence of the UMCG. There were seven characterizing criteria useable for the identification for UMCG. Upon matching them to the Irish criteria for serum cryoglobulin, some modifications are being proposed to the 16th standards that has been formulated and built as an Irish criterion. The existence of UMCG is being reported for the first time in human chronic infectious bacterial disease.

Keywords : urinary, mucosal, cryoglobulin, standard immunofixation

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